

Foods
2024
Conference

The 5th International Electronic Conference on Foods

28–30 October 2024 | Online

Program and Abstract Book

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The 5th International Electronic Conference on Foods

28–30 October 2024| Online

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Welcome from the Chair

Dear Colleagues,

We sincerely appreciate all scholars for their participation in the last four international e-conferences of Foods since 2021. Once again, Foods is delighted to host **the 5th Electronic Conference—The Future of Technology, Sustainability, and Nutrition in the Food Domain**, in a virtual format on **October 28–30, 2024**. The conference will focus on critical themes such as cutting-edge food science and technology, nutritional health, and research to promote sustainable technological innovation in the food domain and address the challenges posed by food safety, food security, and nutritional/dietary demands.

The future of the food industry faces many challenges in a fast-paced world, including the disruptiveness of new technologies, the fragility of ecosystems, the instability of economies, and the reflection of humanity's higher demands for nutritional health and food safety.

Food sustainability is paramount in the future, so nutrition-oriented dietary needs have gradually led to nutritional trends, food cultures, and food policies. This transformational change in nutrition-oriented food sustainability requires innovative food science and emerging food technologies as the key to development in the food industry. Emerging food technologies can help materialize the fast-paced changing transitions in food processing, food production systems, food demand, food waste management, etc. Such technologies are taking shape in the food industry through digitized food science, such as Big Data, the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning, Drones, new physical systems, and Genetic Technologies.

As a multidisciplinary, cross-fertilized field, the future of food science should be centered on emerging technologies oriented toward nutrition and sustainability. Combined with digital food science, the interaction between food nutrition and sustainability should be a priority. Therefore, we would like this Conference to focus on the following sections:

Session 1: Innovation in Food Technology and Engineering

Session 2: Food Nutrition and Functional Foods

Session 3: Sustainable Food Security and Food Systems

Session 4: Food Microbiology

Session 5: Chemistry and Physicochemical Properties of Foods

Session 6: Emerging Methods of Food Analysis

Session 7: Novel Preservation and Packaging Technologies

Session 8: Food Quality and Safety

Session 9: Food Cultures, Policy and Consumer Science

Session 10: Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning in The Food Industry

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we cordially invite you to join us at the 5th International Electronic Conference on Foods.

We look forward to your contributions.

Prof. Dr. Arun K. Bhunia
Conference Chair

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- **Journal Rank:** JCR - Q1 (Food Science and Technology) / CiteScore - Q1 (Health Professions (miscellaneous))
- **Rapid Publication:** manuscripts are peer-reviewed and a first decision is provided to authors approximately 14.3 days after submission; acceptance to publication is undertaken in 2.8 days (median values for papers published in this journal in the first half of 2024).
- **Recognition of Reviewers:** reviewers who provide timely, thorough peer-review reports receive vouchers entitling them to a discount on the APC of their next publication in any MDPI journal, in appreciation of the work done.

Impact Factor: 4.7 (2023); 5-Year Impact Factor: 5.1 (2023)

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Program at a Glance

	Day 1	Day 2		Day 3
Morning	S3. Sustainable Food Security and Food System 08:00 AM CET	Parallel Sessions		S6. Emerging Methods of Food Analysis 10:00 AM CET
		S4. Foods Microbiology S7. Novel Preservation and Packaging Technologies 09:00-11:50 AM CET	S2. Food Nutrition and Functional Foods 10:00-11:30 AM CET	
Afternoon	S1. Innovation in Food Technology and Engineering 15:00 PM CET	S8. Food Quality and Safety 14:00 PM CET S10. Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning in The Food Industry 16:00 PM CET		Parallel Sessions
		S5. Chemistry and Physicochemical Properties of Foods 14:30-16:40 PM CET	S9. Food Cultures, Policy and Consumer Science 14:00-15:50 PM CET	

Foods2024 Program

28th October 2024 (Monday)

S3. Sustainable Food Security and Food System

8:00 AM (CET, Basel) | 03:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 15:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
08:00–08:10	Prof. Dr. Arun K. Bhunia Conference Chair	<i>Welcome from the conference chair</i>
08:10–08:15	Prof. Dr. Theodoros Varzakas Session Chair of S3	<i>Welcome from the session chair</i>
08:15–08:40	Prof. Dr. Theodoros Varzakas & Professor Slim Smaoui Keynote Speaker & Invited Speaker	Global food security and sustainability: the road to 2030 and forward
08:40–09:00	Professor Maria Papageorgiou & Dr. Andriana Skendi Invited Speakers	High protein substitute in gluten free bread as a means of food security and sustainability
09:00–09:20	Professor Sofia Agriopoulou Invited Speaker	Occurrence, detection and control strategies of mycotoxins in fruits and vegetables as a means of food security and sustainability
09:20–09:35	Jocelyn C. Lee Selected Speaker	Case Studies of Small-Medium Enterprises Around the World: Major Constraints and Benefits from the Implementation of Food Safety Management Systems
09:35–09:50	Hui Cao Selected Speaker	Study on the effect of flavonoids on the formation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in barbecued food and its mechanism

S1. Innovation in Food Technology and Engineering

15:00 PM (CET, Basel) | 10:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 22:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
15:00–15:10	Dr. Mohsen Gavahian Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the session chair</i>
15:10–15:30	Prof. Dr. Vida Šimat Invited Speaker	Challenges and opportunities of using by-products for innovative technological and functional food applications
15:30–15:50	Dr. Elsa M. Gonçalves Invited Speaker	Innovation and Technological Challenges in Plant-Based Food Products
15:50–16:05	Diana Pinto Selected Speaker	From Salt Marshes to the Plate: Could <i>Salicornia ramosissima</i> By-Products be a Promising Functional Ingredient for Foods and Nutraceuticals?
16:05–16:20	Laleh Mozafari Selected Speaker	Effect of the carotene fortification of a cucumber juice on shelf life with extracts from tomato by-products
16:20–16:35	Alessandro Bianchi Selected Speaker	Exploring Alternative Maceration Techniques: Nitrogen vs. Carbonic Maceration in Gamay Variety Wines

29th October 2024 (Tuesday)

S4. Foods Microbiology

S7. Novel Preservation and Packaging Technologies

9:00 AM (CET, Basel) | 04:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 16:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
09:00–09:10	Prof. Dr. Antonio Bevilacqua Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
09:10–09:35	Prof. Dr. Antonio Bevilacqua Keynote Speaker	Food Safety and Risk Assessment
09:35–09:55	Prof. Dr. Antonio Bevilacqua & Mr. Alessandro De Santis Invited Speakers	A Case study on risk assessment
09:55–10:15	Dr. Lorenzo Nissen Invited Speaker	Risk Assessment of xenobiotics-gut microbiota exposure: an in vitro approach to study food-derived microplastics.
10:15–10:35	Dr. Alessandra Barlaam Invited Speaker	Foodborne parasites: rising concerns in food safety, epidemiological trends in Europe and Italy, and future outlooks
10:35–10:50	Antonio Peña-Fernández Selected Speaker	Human-related microsporidian spores in farm chickens from Makeni, Sierra Leone
10:50–11:05	Adriana Silva Selected Speaker	Sustainable antimicrobial strategies: Exploration of grape phenolic extracts for combating foodborne pathogens
11:05–11:20	Filipa Soares Selected Speaker	The Effect of Vacuum Storage on the Preservation of Extra Virgin Olive Oil After Opening
11:20–11:35	Loreta Šernienė Selected Speaker	Microbial Spoilage Mitigation in Biodegradable Cheese Packaging via Protective Lactobacillus Coating
11:35–11:50	Manfred Tacker Selected Speaker	A Comprehensive study including polyethylene-based food packaging and its substitutes on the European market focusing on GWP, water scarcity and fossil energy.

S2. Food Nutrition and Functional Foods

10:00 AM (CET, Basel) | 05:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 17:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
10:00–10:10	Prof. Dr. Antonello Santini Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
10:10–10:30	Dr. Michael Netzel Invited Speaker	Halophytes – “Salty Champions” for a Healthy Nutrition(?)
10:30–10:45	Vanesa Sánchez-Martín Selected Speaker	Coffee leaves: a natural source of compounds for reducing body fat accumulation
10:45–11:00	Rafik Balti Selected Speaker	Enzymatic strategy to valorize two red macroalgae species for bioactive peptide production as promising nutraceuticals
11:00–11:15	Tatiane Cristina Gonçalves de Oliveira Selected Speaker	Circular economy in the agri-food sector: valorization studies of vegetable by-products
11:15–11:30	Christophe Espírito Santo Selected Speaker	Innovative dehydrated snack using low-value horticultural products: Beetroot, apple and orange, a crispy combination

S8. Food Quality and Safety

14:00 PM (CET, Basel) | 09:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 21:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
14:00–14:10	Prof. Dr. Antonello Santini Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
14:10–14:30	Dr. Dirk W. Lachenmeier Invited Speaker	Acrylamide in Ultra-Light Coffee Roasts: A Safety Assessment
14:30–14:45	Mojca Jevšnik Selected Speaker	Food hygiene behaviour improvement with nudge tools
14:45–15:00	Yara Bulha Loforte Loforte Selected Speaker	Modelling the microbial competition of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and selected lactic acid bacteria strains in reconstituted milk
15:00–15:15	António Pereira Selected Speaker	Olive Oil Authenticity: A Critical Issue in Non-Regulated Markets
15:15–15:30	Aida Dama Selected Speaker	Origanum vulgare essential oil from Southern Albania: preliminary results.
15:30–15:45	Ariana Macieira Selected Speaker	A case study about the perception of food safety in consumers of fresh produce from local and small farms in the North of Portugal

SHORT BREAK

S10. Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning in The Food Industry

16:00 PM (CET, Basel) | 11:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 23:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
16:00–16:10	Assoc. Prof. Yonghui Li Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
16:10–16:35	Assoc. Prof. Yonghui Li Keynote Speaker	Use of machine learning in predicting protein solubility
16:35–16:55	Prof. Dr. Minwei Xu Invited Speaker	Predictive Modeling of Tofu Quality: Leveraging Protein Subunit Profiles and AI
16:55–17:15	Assoc. Prof. Davood B. Pourkargar Invited Speaker	Physics-Informed Machine Learning Modeling for Characterization and Control of Plant-based Meat Processing Systems
17:15–17:35	Dr. Zhang Dachuan Invited Speaker	Deep Learning Enables Rapid Identification of Food Contaminant-Degrading Enzymes
17:35–17:55	Dr. Lorenzo Guerrini Invited Speaker	Advances in Computer Vision for the Food Industry
17:55–18:10	Azdem Driss Selected Speaker	The application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in the food industry
18:10–18:25	Nandan Kumar Selected Speaker	pLM4CPPs: Protein Language Model-Based Predictor for Cell-Penetrating Peptides
18:25–18:40	Hyukjin Kwon Selected Speaker	Bioinformatical characterization and machine learning classification of seed storage proteins

30th October 2024 (Wednesday)**S6. Emerging Methods of Food Analysis****10:00 AM (CET, Basel) | 05:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 17:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)**

CET Time	Speaker	Title
10:00–10:10	Prof. Dr. Susana Casal Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
10:10–10:30	Dr. Roberta Foligni Invited Speaker	Potential Of Edible Insect Hydrolyzed to formulate innovative food products: effect on Tecno-functional properties and exploring “remote home tasting
10:30–10:45	Dr. Sónia Soares Invited Speaker	DNA-Based Approaches for Evaluating Honey Quality and Authenticity: Advances and Future Directions
10:45–11:00	Bruna Carbas Selected Speaker	Detection of Fumonisin in Maize Using Near-Infrared Spectroscopy
11:00–11:15	Agata Fabiszewska Selected Speaker	The use of the ft-ir technique to predict the content of oleaginous yeast biomass
11:15–11:30	Sureerat Makmuang Selected Speaker	Quantitative and qualitative evaluation of microplastic contamination of shrimp using Vis-NIR multispectral imaging technology combined with a modified self-organizing map

S9. Food Cultures, Policy and Consumer Science**14:00 PM (CET, Basel) | 09:00 AM (EDT, New York) | 21:00 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)**

CET Time	Speaker	Title
14:00–14:10	Prof. Dr. Igor Tomasevic Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
14:10–14:30	Dr. Maurice O’Sullivan Invited Speaker	Senory Driven Nutritional Optimisation of Foods
14:30–14:50	Dr. Luís Miguel Cunha Invited Speaker	New perspectives on the use of insects as food: findings from a decade of consumer studies, from attitudes to hedonics and behaviour
14:50–15:05	Sofia Sousa Selected Speaker	Determinants of cow’s milk and plant-based milk substitute consumption: cross-cultural study of Portuguese and Irish young adults
15:05–15:20	Mirlian Elva Selected Speaker	The Living History Connoisseur—an unexpected consumer of traditional fermented products
15:20–15:35	Pascal Ohlhausen Selected Speaker	Evaluation of food waste reduction in German private households— Development of an app approach
15:35–15:50	Anastasia Fountouli Selected Speaker	Unveiling consumers’ awareness, attitudes and motivations behind entomophagy in Greece: A Theory of Planned Behavior approach

S5. Chemistry and Physicochemical Properties of Foods

14:30 PM (CET, Basel) | 09:30 AM (EDT, New York) | 21:30 PM (CST Asia, Beijing)

CET Time	Speaker	Title
14:30–14:40	Dr. Joana S. Amaral Session Chair	<i>Welcome from the Session Chair</i>
14:40–15:00	Professor Ana Novo Barros Invited Speaker	Untapped goldmine: unlocking the potential of phenolic compounds in food matrices
15:00–15:20	Dr. Sandrina A. Heleno Invited Speaker	Innovation in foods and beverages through bio-based active agents
15:20–15:40	Dr. Veronica Maria Busch Invited Speaker	Development of Food Ingredients from Neglected and Underutilized Species (NUS) in Argentina
15:40–15:55	Aline Benard Selected Speaker	Functionality and structure of protein isolate from decolorized moringa leaf
15:55–16:10	Demissie Shimelis Gebiba Selected Speaker	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and cytotoxic potential of ethanolic leaf extracts from <i>Englerina woodfordiodes</i> M. Gilbert and <i>Oncocalyx fischeri</i> (Ebg.) M. Gilbert
16:10–16:25	Antonella Lamonaca Selected Speaker	Proteomic profiling of lentil varieties by discovery high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry: nutritional, safety and authenticity perspectives
16:25–16:40	Shakrurah Azeez Selected Speaker	Effect of growth stages on polyphenols and secondary metabolites of haskap leaf varieties

sciforum-099358: Modelling the microbial competition of *Listeria monocytogenes* and selected lactic acid bacteria strains in reconstituted milk

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Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and/or their antimicrobial metabolites limit the growth of pathogenic bacteria. This study aims to determine the growth kinetics of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM) in heat-treated reconstituted milk, as affected by three LAB strains from the species *Leuconostoc mesenteroides* (LME), *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* (LP) and *Loigolactobacillus coryniformis* (LC) isolated from goats' milk cheeses. Challenge tests of each LAB strain in monoculture (MC) and coculture (CC) with LM in milk adjusted to three initial pH (5.5, 6.0 and 6.5) were performed. Inoculated milk samples were left to ferment at 12°C for 8 days. A pH-driven dynamic growth model was fitted in separate to the LM and LAB experimental curves from MC and CC; and a Jameson-effect growth model was fitted to the CC growth curves. In MC, LME showed the highest growth rates at the three initial pH levels; whereas in CC, this strain was able to better control the growth of LM, by decreasing their growth rates [day⁻¹] to 1.469 ± 0.205 at pH 5.5; 2.293 ± 0.284 at pH 6.0 and 1.552 ± 0.132 at pH 6.5. LP and LC were only able to inhibit and reduce the growth of LM at pH 5.5. In relation to the maximum concentration of LM (LM_{max}), LME was again the most effective at all initial pH tested. The LM_{max} [ln CFU/ml] values were reduced to 15.05 ± 0.367; 16.32 ± 0.204 and 16.91 ± 0.132 at pH 5.5; 6.0 and 6.5, in comparison to the values obtained in MC (20.85 ± 0.060; 21.10 ± 0.212 and 21.31 ± 0.085, respectively). This indicates that the strain of LME has a broader and more inhibitory effect on LM growth across different pH, whereas the strains of LP and LC are effective in more acidic conditions. These results provide insights into the use of LAB as a natural biopreservative in dairy products.

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